

Impact of Surface Water Storage on quality of Ground Water for Kachchh Region of Gujarat

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ABSTRACT

The rainfall in Kachchh District is very scanty and irregular and the district has very few rainy days. There are 81 rivers in Kachchh district alone, however all are non-perennial rivers. The geology of Kachchh District varies from taluka to taluka. Most of the geology of the state consists of sandy strata with high permeability. As the region has scanty rainfall, the requirements of water for various purposes like domestic water supply, irrigation as well as industrial use is fulfilled by utilization of ground water. As a result, ground water consists of 90 percent of the water supply for domestic use as well as for irrigation purposes. As a result, it sometimes leads to over extraction of ground water. As the region consists of sandy strata, the surface water which is stored due to construction of dams and other micro-structures slowly percolates and recharges the ground water. As the geology in the region varies and the quantity of rainfall and number of rainy days vary from taluka to taluka, the pattern of ground water recharge will also vary. Through this paper it is attempted to study the Impact of Surface Water Storage on quality of Ground Water for Kachchh Region of Gujarat

INTRODUCTION

Kachchh district stretches roughly from 22°44'11" (approx.) to 24°41'25" (approx.) north latitudes and 68°09'46" (approx.) and 71°54'47" (approx.) east longitudes. It is bounded on the north and north-west by Sindh (Pakistan), on the north-east by Rajasthan, on the east by the districts of Banaskantha and Mehsana, on the south-east by Surendranagar district, on the south by the Gulf of Kutch and the Rajkot district and on the south-west and west by the Arabian Sea.

RIVERS OF KACHCHH

The rivers of the district have certain characteristics. Firstly, all the rivers or streams of Kachchh start from its central portion and flow towards the sea in the south and the Great Rann in the north and the Little Rann in the south-east. Broadly speaking the rivers flow northwards or southwards because of the ranges in the central area which serve as water sheds. There are physical contours varying from 16 km. to 32 km. which create independent flows of water. As a result, there is one river at every 24 km. in the district.

The rivers are non-perennial. With short non-perennial rivers and scanty rainfall, there is no flood problem in the district. The rivers have steep gradients and are flashy. They have therefore formed deep cuts along their courses and rarely spill over their banks. Duration of flow of water in the rivers takes place for a few hours in monsoon. As such, there are no chances for the rivers and streams to change their original courses. Some rivers are called by different names of villages by which they pass. This is particularly the case with small rivers.

RAINFALL PATTERN IN KACHCHH

The annual rainfall in the district is 322.2 mm (12.69"). The normal rainfall in the district ranges between 300 to 400 mm. It varies from 407.5 mm (16.5") at Mandavi on the southern coast to 249.4 mm (9.81") at Lakhpat on the north-west coast. Most of annual rainfall in the district is received during the south-west monsoon season, July being the rainiest month. The variation in the annual rainfall from the year to year is very large. On an average there are 14 rainy days in a year in the district. This number decreases from 17 at Mandavi and Rapar on the south coast to 9 at Lakhpat and Khadir in the north.

GEOLOGY OF KACHCHH

The soils of Kutch can be mainly classified into:

(1) Desert (2) alluvial sandy (3) medium black (4) saline alkaline

Though other types such as loamy, silty and clayey are also found at certain places, the northern part of the district is dominated by desert and sandy soils which are mostly salt affected soils. Proceeding southwards, the interior area is composed of either sandy or medium black soils. The southern part of the district comprising the coastal area around Mandavi and Mundra has saline soils suitable for cultivation. The eastern part is mostly plain with some rocky patches where the

soil is sandy with clay and alluvial loam in some parts. The central portion is hilly and rocky with strips of cultivable lands along the lower slopes.

Table 1 Types of Soils

Sr.No.	Type of Soil	Taluka
1	Clayey	Mundra
2	Sandy Clay	Bhuj Anjar Rapar Nakhatrana
3	Clayey & Medium black	Lakhpat Mandvi Abdasa
4	Sandy, Clayey & Medium Black	Bhachau

SURFACE WATER STORAGE

As the rainfall pattern is very irregular and rainfall being scanty, there are no Major Irrigation Schemes in Kachchh. There are 25 Medium Irrigation Schemes and 165 Minor Irrigation Schemes in Kachchh. All the medium as well as minor irrigation schemes are used for domestic water supply to near by villages as well. Besides this there are number of micro structures like checkdams and underground check dams

GROUND WATER DEVELOPMENT

As most of the area is sandy strata, the surface water infiltrates into the soil. Thus ground water is a major source for domestic water supply as well as for water supply for irrigation and industrial use. The following table shows the number of government tubewells in various talukas of Kachchh District.

Table 2 Number of Tube wells

Sr.no	Taluka	No.of tube wells
1	Anjar	13
2	Mandavi	21
3	Nakhtrana	34
4	Bhuj	57
5	Mundra	7
6	Bhachau	10
7	Rapar	10
8	Lakhpat	2
9	Total	154

Table 3 Ground Water Development in Kachchh

Sr.No.	% Development of Ground Water Table	Talukas Covered
1	Less than 10%	-
2	10.1% to 15%	Lakhpat
3	15.1% to 25%	-
4	25.1% to 65%	Bhuj
5	More than 65.1%	Mandvi, Nakhatrana, Bhachau, Anjar, Rapar, Abdasa, Mundra

RAINFALL AND STORAGE IN MEDIUM IRRIGATION SCHEMES

GROUND WATER TABLE FLUCTUATIONS

The number of medium irrigation schemes as well as minor irrigation schemes and check dams and other microstructures are responsible for the surface water storage. As the number of such structures has increased with the passage of years, the surface storage in the region has increased. As most of the area consists of sandy soil and therefore most of the surface water stored is converted to ground water.

The following plates show the water level fluctuations for the duration of 1993 to 2002

REFERENCES

1. “Effect of Earthquakes on Medium Irrigation Schemes of Kachchh District” M.E.Dissertation by Mrs. Sanskriti S. Mujumdar (November 2001) guided by Prof. P.N.Sutaria & Dr. A.S.Patel
2. Prof. P.N.Sutaria & Dr. A.S.Patel & Mrs. S.S.Mujumdar (2002) “Drinking water management for summer season in an earthquake affected severely drought prone region- Kachchh, A Case Study” – a paper presented in One Day State Level Seminar on Sustainable Water Management organized by Indian Water Works Association, Vadodara Chapter.
3. Dr.A.S.Patel, Mrs. S.S.Mujumdar (2008) “Water Resources Management for Arid Regions – Kachchh A Case Study” – a paper to be presented in Two Day National Conference on Water Conservation and Artificial Recharge organized by Civil Engg. Dept. Fac. Of Tech. & Engg. M.S.U. Baroda.
4. Dr. A.S.Patel, Mrs. S.S.Mujumdar (2008) “Study of Ground Water Table Fluctuations for Kachchh District of Gujarat” – a paper to be presented in Two Day National Conference on Water Conservation and Artificial Recharge organized by Civil Engg. Dept. Fac. Of Tech. & Engg. M.S.U. Baroda.

ANNEXURES

1. Plate 1 Rivers and locations of medium irrigation schemes.
2. Plate 2 Topography of Kachchh District
3. Plate 3 Rainfall Pattern of Kachchh District
4. Plate 4 Geology of Kachchh District
5. Plate 5 Area Irrigated by sources

Plate 1 Rivers and locations of medium irrigation schemes	Plate 2 Topography of Kachchh District
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Plate 3 Rainfall Pattern of Kachchh District

Plate 4 Geology of Kachchh District

Plate 5 Area Irrigated by sources in Kachchh District

Plate 6 Ground Water Development in Kachchh District

